

Kinetics of Oxidation of Some Aldoximes by Thallium(III) Acetate. Part II

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The kinetics of oxidative hydrolysis of acetaldoxime(AAO), propionaldoxime(PAO), butyraldoxime(BAO) and benzaldoxime(BNAO) leading to carbonyl compounds have been examined. The second-order rate constants (k_2), the Arrhenius energy of activation (E_a), the frequency factor (A), the entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) and the free-energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) were evaluated and discussed. A mechanism in accordance with the kinetic data is proposed.

AFTER the first report¹ on the formation of carbonyl compounds from oximes by the action of thallium(III) nitrate in methanol, kinetic investigation² established that these reactions were total second order-first order with respect to each reactant. McKillop *et al*¹ explained the formation of carbonyl compounds through a two step mechanism and also suggested that the carbonyl compounds may also be formed via iminoxy radicals. We now report the results of a kinetic study on the oxidation of some aldoximes in 50%(v/v) aqueous acetic acid.

Materials and Methods :

Thallium(III) acetate was prepared by a known method³. Acetaldoxime, propionaldoxime and butyraldoxime were prepared using the method of Beech⁴. α (or Syn) benzaldoxime was prepared by a standard method⁵. Sulphuric acid (Basynt A.R., India; Sp. Gr. 1.8), sodium bisulphate (E. Merck, Germany), thallos sulphate (L.R., B.D.H.) triethylamine (A.R., B.D.H.) and all other chemicals used were of Analar grade. All the experiments were conducted in 50%(v/v) aqueous acetic acid.

The kinetic runs were carried out in pyrex glass tubes of capacity 80 ml provided with an inlet and an outlet. Blowing in through the inlet causes the effective mixing of the solutions. Measured quantities of the solutions of oxime, acid (H_2SO_4), sodium bisulphate and water were kept in a thermostat maintained at a particular temperature with an accuracy of $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Thallium(III) acetate solution was also kept in the same thermostat. Required volume of the oxidant solution was added to the mixture. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted thallium(III) acetate iodometrically.

Results and Discussion

Effect of Varying [Tl(III)] and [oxime] :

At constant [oxime] ($\sim 0.02M$ for all the oximes), (H_2SO_4) (1.0M), μ (1.2M) and temperature (30°), a

first order dependence with respect to Tl^{3+} was observed. From the linear plots of $\log[Tl^{3+}]$ vs time, the pseudomolecular rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated. At constant $[Tl^{3+}]$ ($1.25 \times 10^{-2}M$), H_2SO_4 (1.0M), μ (1.2M) and temperature (30°), variations of excess of [oxime] (0.008-0.02M) gave increasing rates with increasing [oxime]. Plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs \log [oxime] were linear and the slope (i.e., the order with respect to oxime) is unity.

Effect of Varying [H^+] and μ :

Increase in acid concentration had no effect on the rate of oxidation of all the oximes. When the ionic strength was increased by the addition of sodium bisulphate solution, the rate was unaffected which indicates that neutral species were involved in the reaction, i.e., $Tl(OAc)_3$ seems to be the active species in aldoxime oxidation reactions.

Effect of initially added Tl(I) :

Addition of thallos sulphate (0.00 to 0.025M) had no effect on the rate of oxidation of all the substrates.

Effect of initially added Triethylamine :

When triethylamine (0.00-0.02M) was added to the reaction mixture, the rate of oxidation was enhanced considerably. If there is a complex formation between Tl^{3+} and the tertiary amine, one would expect a decrease in rate (Table 1).

TABLE I—EFFECT OF INITIALLY ADDED TRIETHYLAMINE(TEA)

[TEA] $\times 10^2 M$	AAO	PAO	BAO	BNAO
	$-R_{Tl^{3+}} \times 10^5$ m/l/s	$-R_{Tl^{3+}} \times 10^5$ m/l/s	[TEA] $\times 10^{-2}$ M	$-R_{Tl^{3+}} \times 10^5$ m/l/s
0.00	1.14	9.40	0.00	8.67
5.00	1.72	10.82	4.00	9.67
10.00	2.17	11.65	8.00	13.83
15.00	2.48	13.21	12.00	14.00
20.00	2.73	15.72	16.00	14.95

The deoxygenation of oximes proceeds at measurable rates in the temperature range 20-35° and the oxidation of water is negligible under the experimental conditions. The order with respect to thallium(III) acetate and substrate(oxime) is one each. The redox system, $Tl^{3+} + Oxime$, initiate vinyl polymerization indicating the formation of a radical. In any metal ion oxidation of oximes the radical formed in the first step is reported to be iminoxy radical and this may cause the initiation. The iminoxy radical may be formed via an inner-sphere mechanism or an outer-sphere mechanism. If the radical is formed via an inner-sphere mechanism the increase in $[H^+]$ will have to decrease the rate. The fact that increase of $[H^+]$ does not effect the rate indicates that the iminoxy radical is formed via an outer-sphere mechanism. Gilbert and Norman⁶ investigated the decay of some iminoxy radicals produced in the oxidation of oximes by lead tetraacetate in methylene chloride in the absence of oxygen and found the kinetics to be first order with respect to the iminoxy radicals. So the basic question arises. In the thallium(III) acetate oxidation of oximes which is the rate-limiting step, i.e., is it the formation of the radical or the decay of the radicals to products. Lown^{7,8} had pointed out that the addition of tertiary base increased the concentration of iminoxy radicals. If the formation of the radical is the slow-step, the rate will be affected by the addition of a tertiary base like triethylamine; the rate was increased considerably (Table 1).

The formation of iminoxy radical suggests that thallium(III) acts as one-electron oxidant, i.e., thallium(II) is formed as an intermediate. But for a solitary report⁹, there is not much evidence for the reaction between thallium(III) and the radical. Thallium(II) formed as a transient species may react with the oxime or the radical. The possibility of a reaction between thallium(II) and oxime may be neglected because the reaction between the radical and thallium(II) is expected to be many times faster than the former one. The stoichiometry and product analysis indicated that thallium(II) was involved only in the main reaction and not in some secondary reactions. Thus thallium(II) reacts with iminoxy radical in the presence of water to form hydroxy nitroso compounds. The dimerization and decomposition of nitroso compounds are discussed by Gowenlock¹⁰ and the formation of $H_2N_2O_2$ was also postulated as the intermediate in the oxidation of hydroxylamine by thallium(III) acetate¹¹. The product analyses for all the oximes showed that the

products were carbonyl compounds in high yield (95%). The stoichiometry of the reaction is 1 : 1, i.e., for every molecule of oxime one $Tl(III)$ was required. Based on these foregoing arguments, the following mechanism may be proposed :

Rate and thermodynamic parameters and their interpretation :

The oxidation of oximes follows the rate expression

$$-\frac{d[Tl(III)]}{dt} = k_2[\text{Substrate}][Tl(III)]$$

The second-order rate constants have been obtained at different temperatures by plotting $\log k_{psendo}$ vs [oxime]₀ (Table 2). From a plot of $\log k_2$ vs $1/T$, the Arrhenius energy of activation (E_a), A , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger values have been calculated (Table 3). The

TABLE 3—KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR ALDOXIMES

Substrate	E_a K cal/mole	A $M^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$	ΔS^\ddagger ou	ΔG^\ddagger K cal/mole
AAO	11.6	9.404×10^6	-21.2	18.0
PAO	18.9	4.879×10^6	-18.8	19.6
BAO	19.1	4.869×10^{12}	-0.7	19.3
BNAO	28.2	3.335×10^{18}	26.2	20.3

E_a values for all the oximes range from 10 to 30 K cal/mole and this is in agreement with oxidation reactions by other oxidants where free radical mechanisms were proposed. ΔG^\ddagger values are more or less the same may be understood in terms of isokinetic relationship; according to this principle for a series of homologous substrates of slightly different structures but undergoing reaction by the same mechanism, the free energy, ΔG^\ddagger will be the same with relative changes in ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger . This also supports the unified mechanism proposed.

The rate-limiting step is the decomposition of the outer-sphere complex to give the iminoxy radical and it is generally accepted that if a radical is produced in the slow step, then the stability of the radical may increase the oxidation of the parent compound. The aldoximes are oxidised in the following order $BAO > PAO = AAO$ and benzaldoxime is oxidised slower than the aliphatic aldoximes. If the stability of the iminoxy radical

TABLE 2—SECOND-ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR ALDOXIMES

Substrate	$[H^+] = 1.0M$			
	$20 \pm 0.1^\circ$	$25 \pm 0.1^\circ$	$30 \pm 0.1^\circ$	$35 \pm 0.1^\circ$
AAO	20.80	26.80	40.30	—
PAO	21.20	27.80	46.60	—
BAO	25.10	43.30	74.20	—
BNAO	—	7.00	15.60	32.90

is considered in the former case, the stability of the radicals

may not vary much and it is expected that the rate of oxidation should remain the same. The observation that the higher homologue is oxidised faster than the lower homologues was also supported by Yukawa *et al*¹² in their study on the oxidation of some straight chain aldoximes. The yield of oxidation products is in the following order :

This order may be assumed as an approximate measure of the rate of oxidation from the fact that (i) the oxidation reaction is not an equilibrium reaction, (ii) there seems to be no side reaction and (iii) the carbonyl compounds are formed by a similar mechanism. The above conditions hold good for the oxidation of aldoximes studied and so the order is expected.

Acetaldoxime is oxidised faster than benzaldoxime which means that iminoxy radical from

acetaldoxime is more stable than the radical from benzaldoxime. The radical formed in the latter substrate is not interacting with the π -system, i.e., the radical formed is of σ -type and not of π -type.

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